

The Komaggas palp footed spider *Palpimanus paroculus* Simon, 1910 from South Africa (Araneae: Palpimanidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Wynand Uys², Cecile Roux³ & Peter Webb³

¹DSI/NRF Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change, University of Venda (dippenaaransie@gmail.com); ² Environmental Consultant, Hoedspruit (wynand@ottersden.co.za); ³ iNaturalist photographers

ABSTRACT: The spider *Palpimanus paroculus* Simon, 1910 was described from Komaggas in the Northern Cape in 1910. In the first spider atlas of 2010, it was still only known from the type locality. Since then, it has been recorded during surveys undertaken in the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve in 2013 and surveys in the Richtersveld National Park. The type material of the species in the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (Germany) was re-examined in 2019, and more information became available. The general morphology of the species is provided based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

The Palpimanidae is a spider family assigned to 20 genera (World Spider Catalog, 2025). *Palpimanus* Dufour, 1820 is the second largest genus in the family, with 43 species currently known from the West Palearctic, Africa and South America. To date, 21 species of *Palpimanus* are known to occur in Africa, south of the Sahara and 14 from South Africa. The African species have not yet been revised except that the type material of four species in the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (Germany) was redescribed by Zonstein & Marusik (2019).

One of the four was the spider *Palpimanus paroculus* Simon, 1910, that was described from Komaggas in the Northern Cape in 1910. Little is known about the species, and in the first spider atlas of 2010, it was still only known from the type locality. The species has been recorded during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), in the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2018) in 2013 and surveys in the Richtersveld National Park (Haddad *et al.* 2025). More information on the species became available with the publication of Zonstein & Marusik (2019) and several specimens on iNaturalist have been recognised.

The general morphology of the species is provided based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Palpimanus paroculus Simon, 1910

Palpimanus paroculus Simon, 1910: 179; Griffin and Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991: 158; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2010; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 18; Zonstein & Marusik 2019: 89.

Diagnosis: Female total length: 5 mm. Cephalothorax: dark purple, densely granulated and covered with long, ash-white setae (Fig. 1). Anterior eyes are small, equal in size, and arranged in a slightly curved line (Fig. 2). The median eyes are distinctly farther from the lateral eyes than the lateral eyes are from each other. Posterior eyes minute, forming a perfectly straight line when viewed from above; the median eyes are farther from the lateral eyes than the lateral eyes are from each other, with the interocular space at least three times wider than the diameter of an eye. Median eye area: more than three times longer than wide, and much narrower in front than behind. Abdomen brick-coloured, densely covered with ash-white pubescence (Fig. 3); the epigastric region is somewhat hardened, posteriorly almost straightly truncated, anteriorly black and wrinkled, strongly transversely striated toward the pedicel.

Figures 1–3. *Palpimanus paroculus* female. 1. Dorsal view. 2. Anterior view. 3. Female with an egg sac. Credits: 1. Cecile Roux. 2–3. Peter Webb.

Chelicerae and sternum dark. Anterior legs thick, reddish-chestnut to nearly black. Remaining legs dark tawny-reddish, with femora slightly lighter in colour. Epigyne with an broad epigynal scutum (Fig. 4). Male unknown.

LIFESTYLE

The species is a free-living ground dweller and it has been recorded from the more arid Desert, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent Karoo Biomes. In the Tswalu Game Reserve, a female with an egg sac was photographed (Fig. 6-8). The female deposited the round white egg sac in a retreat made of small stones and plant material held together by silk threads. The provided some protection for the eggs. At Richtersveld National Park, six specimens were hand collected from leaf litter (Haddad *et al.*, 2025).

DISTRIBUTION

The distribution of *P. paroculus* is shown in Fig. 13. Simon (1910) described the first female from Kommagas (then Kammagas) in the Namakwa District Municipality, Northern Cape.

During surveys of SANSA, it was sampled from the Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018) and from the Richtersveld National Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2025), both from the Northern Cape. In the World Spider Catalog (2025), the species is also listed from Namibia. However, Griffin and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991) stated that there are no confirmed published records from Namibia, and they only refer to Simon (1910) with a record from South Africa.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa (Fig. 13).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Lectotype *Northern Cape Province*, Komaggas (original “Kammagas”)(-29.75, 17.4). SANSA surveys: Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Richtersveld National Park (-28.25, 17.17)

Figure 13. Distribution records of *Palpimanus paroculus* in South Africa. Showing the type locality, the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Palpimanus paroculus* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

Figures 6–12. *Palpimanus paroculus*. 6–8. Female busy constructing retreat for egg sac. 9. Juvenile. 10. Epigastral scutum. 11–12. Adult females showing the variation in abdomen colour. Credits: 6–8, 11. Peter Webb. 9 & 12. Cecile Roux. 10. Charles Haddad.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The status of the species remains obscure. It is presently only known from the Northern Cape Province. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons. However the species received some protection in the following protected areas: Meerkat National Park, Richtersveld National Park, Tswalu Kalahari Reserve and Witsand Nature Reserve.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank the photographers for sharing their photographs on Inaturalist and Charles Haddad for Fig. 10.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L. N. 2020. *The Palpimanidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 25 pp. <https://doi:10.5281/zenodo.6813794>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). South African National Survey of Arachnida Technical Report 2010 version 1 1160 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628809>
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., FOORD S.H. & JOCQUE R. 2018. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve in the Northern Cape province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 60(1), a1486. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v60i1.1486>
- GRIFFIN E. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 1991. A checklist of, and references to, the Namibian spider fauna Arachnida, Araneae). *Cimbebasia* 13: 155–181.
- HADDAD C.R., BOOYSEN R., VICKERS M.E., CHRISTIAAN R., STANDER A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2025. A little goes a long way: a rapid sampling protocol repeated seasonally generates considerable spider biodiversity data in an arid national park. *Biodiversity and Conservation* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-025-03107-9>
- SIMON E. 1910. Arachnoidea. Araneae (ii). In: Schultze L (Ed.) Zoologische und anthropologische Ergebnisse einer Forschungsreise im Westlichen und zentralen Südafrika. *Denkschriften der Medizinisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena* 16, 175–218. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.51355>
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2025. World Spider Catalog. <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, version 20.0 [Accessed 25.09.2025]
- ZONSTEIN S.L. & MARUSIK Y.M. 2019. On the revisited types of four poorly known African species of *Palpimanus* (Araneae, Palpimanidae) *African Invertebrates* 60(1): 83–95. [doi:10.3897/AfrInvertebr.60.34229](https://doi.org/10.3897/AfrInvertebr.60.34229)